

Analysis of the Ignition Products of Unsymmetrical Dimethyl Hydrazine with Nitric Acid and the Probable Reaction Mechanism

S. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, R. D. S. College, Muzaffarpur

and

R. K. PRASAD*

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur

Manuscript received 4 January 1982, revised 22 September 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

The reaction products of unsymmetrical dimethyl hydrazine (UDMH) with nitric acid, under ignition and near ignition conditions have been examined through methods of instrumental analysis. Spectroscopic methods which include uv, ir, nmr and mass spectra have been used for the liquid products and gas chromatography for the gaseous and the liquid products. A mechanism for the reaction is proposed on the basis of the known chemistry of UDMH and HNO_3 , as well as reactions and intermediates that are known and on analogous reactions of similar reagents.

ALTHOUGH unsymmetrical dimethyl hydrazine (UDMH) and nitric acid ignite spontaneously on contact at atmospheric pressure it is suspected that at very low pressure existing in upper space the ignition may not occur and the mixture may undergo different reaction. Such behaviour is reported in the case of N_2O_4 and hydrazine or its alkyl derivatives¹. The formation of some less volatile products may also be suspected. Accumulation of reaction products in the combustion chamber of rockets is dangerous because they are potentially explosive and can detonate. It is, therefore, essential to know the nature of reaction products of UDMH and concentrated HNO_3 on ignition and also under non-ignition conditions.

In the reaction of hydrazine with N_2O_4 , Sawyer and Glassman² detected nitrosamine and NH_3 as intermediates. Mayer, Faylor and Schiler³ analysed the pre-ignition residues of the reaction of hydrazine and alkyl hydrazines and detected the corresponding nitrosamines through mass spectrometry and the nitrates of hydrazines through infrared spectra. Other workers⁴⁻⁶ have also reported that at low temperature N_2O_4 reacts with hydrazine to form solid intermediate product identified as hydrazinium nitrate. In the present work a similar physicochemical analysis of the reaction products of UDMH and concentrated HNO_3 is described.

Materials :

Unsymmetrical dimethyl hydrazine (Fluka) and nitric acid (Oster) were used in this study.

Chemical analysis :

The red liquid obtained after ignition was miscible in water and alcohol. Continuous ether extraction gave a small amount of the red liquid. A peculiar observation was made. A corked sample tube containing about 1 ml of the ethereal extract was in hand. After 10 min, it became hot and suddenly started boiling giving brown fumes. The temperature of the boiling liquid was found to be 117° .

10 ml of the red liquid was distilled under reduced pressure and the distillate at 125° was collected. At this stage some dense white fumes were seen in the distilling flask, the temperature was seen rising and in no time the liquid in the flask bumped, gave voluminous dense white fumes which had pleasant characteristic smell.

It was suspected that the red liquid was a mixture of several unstable compounds such as organic nitrate and nitrites. One of the suspected products, dimethyl hydrazinium nitrate, was confirmed as follows :

The liquid was taken in a test tube, a pellet of NaOH was added to it and warmed gently. The escaping vapours were passed into alcoholic solution of picric acid. A yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained which, after recrystallization from alcohol, was identified as the picrate of UDMH (m.p. 145.5°).

The same liquid was obtained when the reaction was allowed to occur under non-ignition condition (i.e., when 80-85% HNO_3 was used).

* Author for correspondence.

Spectral analysis :

Ultraviolet spectra : The uv spectra of the sample obtained after extracting with chloroform was recorded on a manual Beckmann ultraviolet spectrophotometer. The plot of $\log \epsilon$ vs wave length (nm) showed a strong absorption at 305 nm ($\log \epsilon_{\max} = 1.8$) which is consistent with the presence of a substance with N=O group⁷.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra were recorded on a Beckmann double beam infrared spectrophotometer of the following three samples in KBr phase :

Sample I : red liquid obtained on (a) ignition in a basin, (b) near ignition.

Sample II : distillate obtained after distilling sample I in a mini distillation assembly.

Sample III : the residual liquid in the distilling flask.

The wave lengths and wave numbers of the various ir bands along with their assignments to the possible modes on the basis of existing literatures^{8,9} have been catalogued in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VIBRATION ASSIGNMENTS FROM THE IR SPECTRA

Sl. No.	Wave length (μ)	Wave number (cm^{-1})	Intensity	Vibration modes
1.	2.8-2.9	3600-3400	v.s.	N-H stretching in (-NH ₂ or NH)
2.	8.2	9100	m	N-H stretching (in amine salts)
3.	3.4-4.3	2900-2700	s	O-H stretching (in -OH ₂)
4.	4.2-4.3	2400-2300	m or w	O-H stretching
5.	5.7-5.8	1750-1725	v.w.	Unassigned
6.	6.1-6.2	1650-1625	s	N-H bending (in prim. or sec. amines)
				O-NO ₂ (in nitrates)
				N-NO ₂ (in nitramines)
7.	7.2-7.3	1400-1380	v.s.	N-NO (nitrosamine)
				O-H bending (in OH ₂)
				O-H bending (in alcohols)
8.	9.2	1090	w	CO stretch in alcohols
9.	9.8	1015	m or w	Aliph. amines
10.	10.5	950	v.w.	N-oxides
11.	12.0-12.1	835-825	s or m	O-N=O or org. nitrates

v.s. = very strong ; s = strong ; m = medium ;
v.w. = very weak ; w = weak.

The positions of the peaks (bands) have been picked up from the five ir spectra of samples I to III and the assignments have been made on the basis of the existing literature^{8,9}.

These spectra reveal the presence of compounds containing -NH₂, =NH, -CH₂, -CN, -NC, -NCO, C-NO₂, N-NO₂ and NO₂⁻ in the product mixture. The presence of dimethyl nitramine is strongly indicated. The spectra of dimethyl nitrosamine recorded by Saad *et al*¹ show peaks at 6.9, 7.6 and 9.48 μ due to N=O, C-N and N-N vibrations, respectively. These bands are absent in the present spectra but a very strong absorption occurring at 7.3 μ may arise due to -N-NO group of nitrosamine. Occurrence of

band in the region 3300-3500 cm^{-1} is assigned to N-H stretch in 2° amine or/and -CONH₂, while the presence of doublets in the same region in some of the samples also indicate 1° amine. A high intensity band in the region 2800-2900 cm^{-1} is safely assigned to C-H stretch due to CH₃ or CH₂ group. Strong absorption in 1650-1625 cm^{-1} region and weak absorption in 1750-1725 cm^{-1} are assigned to C=O stretch in -CONH₂ group or C=N, or -N=N-. Strong absorption at 6.2 μ may be due to -NC or -NCO groups.

The UDMH nitrate has been detected chemically but due to non-availability of a pure sample its spectra could not be recorded. However, the spectra of similar compounds like N₂H₄ nitrate or CH₃-NH.NH₂-nitrate were available and by comparison with the present spectra (band at 12.0-12.1 μ) the nitrate of UDMH in the product was highly indicated.

NMR spectra : The nmr spectra of the following four samples were obtained from Varian-60 NMR spectrometer operating at 60 Mc/s using CCl₄ (for sample I) and CF₃-COOH (for samples II, III and IV) as solvents and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal reference :

Sample I : Pure UDMH

Sample II : Liquid obtained on ignition in a basin.

Sample III : The distillate obtained after distilling the sample II under reduced pressure in a mini-distillation assembly.

Sample IV : The residual liquid in the flask.

UDMH (sample I) presents the simplest of all the spectra with peaks at $\delta = 2.45$ and 3.15 without any splitting pattern. These values and the proton counting from the integration curves are quite consistent with the assumed planar structure in which the six protons of the two methyl and the two protons of the -NH₂ group constitute two magnetically equivalent sets.

The spectrum of sample II shows three prominent bands at $\delta = 2.85$, 3.18 and 5.55. A spin coupling is indicated between the protons due to the first two bands resulting in the multiplicity of peaks but the first order splitting leading to a symmetrical triplet is confined to the first band only ($J = 27.0$ cps). Proton counting in the band system is not consistent with a single pure compound CH₃NH₂ and it seems that the sample contains some (CH₃)₂NH also. The third band is then due to a different molecule. The small peaks at very far down field ($\delta = 6.78$ and 7.7) may be attributed to amide and imide.

The spectrum of sample III exhibits the third and second bands of sample II (the third band shifted by 1.0 ppm towards lower field), while that of sample IV exhibits the triplet structure of the first band of sample II along with all the tiny peaks at $\delta = 6.78$ and 7.7. This leads us to conclude that

the sample obtained after ignition contains (i) one low boiling component and (ii) the comparatively higher boiling components. The strong triplet at $\delta=2.68$ in the case of sample IV may be due to highly shielded methyl protons in the neighbourhood of a $-\text{NH}_2$ group. In the absence of another prominent band in this spectrum and due to the presence of some tiny bands at higher δ values it may be assumed that the residual liquid, sample IV, is a mixture of compounds like $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}_2^+\text{NO}_3^-$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N.NH}_2^+\text{NO}_3^-$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{N}(-\text{CH}_3)_2$, the tiny peaks at far down field being attributed to the HNO_3 protons associated with the amines. The spectrum of sample III shows two bands at $\delta=3.15$ and 6.5 , the former being due to any proton other than CH_3 and the latter representing a larger concentration of protons that are highly unshielded possibly due to some electronegative atom (N or O). But the integration units of the two bands are in the ratio 1 : 6 (approx). It is difficult to assume a single compound of H, O and N with CH_3 group which can conform to these observations.

Mass spectra : The liquid product (undistilled as well as distilled) were analysed on a AEI, England, Model MS 30 DB mass spectrometer. The various peaks (m/e) along with possible assignments are shown in Table 2. The bands above m/e=40 are very weak and may be due to impurities as they are inconsistent with the nature of the reaction under investigation.

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENTS TO THE SPECIES FROM THE MASS SPECTRA

	m/e	Intensity	Fragmentation spectra
Sample No. I (Undistilled ignition product)	44	v.s.	N_2O or CO_2 or NO_2
	63	v.s.	HNO_3 , OH_2 - NO_2 , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}-\text{NH}_2$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NNO}$
	70	m	
	83	v.s.	
	99	s	
	112	s	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}_2$
Sample No. II (Distilled)	124	w	UDMH-nitrate
	44	v.s.	N_2O or CO_2 or NO_2
	55	v.s.	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}$
	63	w	HNO_3 , UDMH, OH_2NO_2 , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NNO}$
	69	v.s.	
	81	v.s.	CH_2NO_2
	95	v.s.	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}-\text{NO}_2$
	109	v.s.	
125	v.s.	UDMH - nitrate	

v.s.=very strong ; s=strong ; m=medium ; w=weak.

In making these assignments, margin has been given to the difference of a maximum of 5 mass units. A peak at m/e=95 is assigned to $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N.NO}_2$ in the distilled sample, while the peaks at 70 in undistilled and 69 in distilled samples correspond to $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N.NO}$ and there is no peak corresponding to CH_3OH and N_2 .

Gas chromatography :

Preparation of samples :

(a) **Gaseous samples :**

Sample I : UDMH solution (1 : 2 dilution with water) was taken in a 500 ml conical flask fitted

with a graduated dropping funnel and an arrangement for the exit of the gases which was further connected to the gas sampler. 20 ml of conc. nitric acid was run from the dropping funnel. Reaction occurred and the gases coming out were collected in the gas sampler after passing through a water cooled trap.

Sample II : Gaseous product of ignition. Equal volumes of UDMH and conc. nitric acid were allowed to ignite in a bomb calorimeter without exhausting the air present in the bomb. The gaseous sample was taken from the bomb by connecting the valve of the bomb to gas chromatograph directly.

(b) **The liquid ignition products :**

5 ml of UDMH was taken in a porcelain dish and 5 ml of conc. nitric acid was added to it with the help of a 5 ml pipette fitted with vacuum pad. After ignition, a red liquid was left in the dish. A portion of the red liquid was kept in a semimicro test tube and marked as sample III. The remaining red liquid was distilled and the distillate was marked as sample IV.

Method of recording gas chromatogram for gaseous samples I and II : Both the samples I and II were separately injected through 10 ml sampling loop into a Beckmann Gas Chromatograph, Model 2A. The other conditions of the instrument were as follows :

Column—7' x 1/4" Teflon, packed with 60/100 coconut charcoal coated with 3% silicon oil 200.

Column temp. -70° ; Injection temp. -120°.
Carrier gas—Helium ; Inlet pressure—29 psi.
Filament current—180 mA.

Chart speed of Westronic recorder—40"/hr on two pan mV/sec. All the runs were isothermal.

Analysis of gaseous samples I and II : The gas chromatograms of samples I and II show four and five peaks, respectively. The peak 1 of sample I is due to NO_2 and air, while the peaks 2 and 3 of samples I and II, respectively are due to NO . The peak 3 for NO in sample II is longer than the peak 2 for NO in sample I. This may be due to the fact that the reaction for collecting sample I was done in an open atmosphere and hence NO formed was oxidised to NO_2 . This logic is strengthened by the appearance of a larger peak (1) for NO_2 with air in sample I as compared to the corresponding peak (2) in sample II, which was collected directly from the bomb in which little air was present.

Gas chromatogram for a known CO_2 standard was also run and a comparison was made between the retention times of CO_2 standard (peak 2) and unidentified peaks of sample I (peaks 3 and 4) and sample II (peaks 3, 4 and 5). It was observed that the peak 3 of sample I and peak 4 of sample II more or less coincide with the peak 2 of the CO_2 standard. Hence these peaks may be assigned to CO_2 or gases like CO , N_2O , etc.

The Porapak Q column was not used here following a report¹⁰ that NO_2 reacts with Porapak Q column.

Analysis of the liquid samples III and IV of ignition products: The analysis of the sample was tried, making use of two different column with temperature programming.

Column packed with coconut charcoal: The details of the instrument were the same as described for the gaseous samples except that the column temperature was 70° at $12'$ and later temperature programming upto 190° and the volume of the sample was 4 ml, taken by micro syringe.

Both the samples show 11 peaks although the concentrations differ from each other. The peaks in sample IV are wider in comparison to those in sample III. This is due to GLSC techniques where diffusion is more than GLC. In sample III all peaks were longer in size than in sample IV excepting peaks 6, 7 and 8. The possible cause may be the change in concentration of the species after distillation.

Peaks 1 to 5 and 9 to 11 of undistilled product in sample III were reduced in size in the distilled product, i. e., sample IV, whereas peaks 6, 7 and 8 of sample III became larger in the distillate sample IV. It seems that peaks 1 to 5 and 9 to 11 of undistilled product are of liquid having somewhat higher boiling point as compared to the compounds represented by peaks 6, 7 and 8. A small proportion of them has gone with the distillate resulting in the decrease of their size. The species represented by peaks 6, 7 and 8 in the undistilled products (sample III) seem to have low boiling points and therefore their greater proportions have gone in the distillate sample IV, causing increase in their size or they have all combined due to close boiling points. A UDMH standard was also run for reference.

The total run on this column could not be carried out as the column could be damaged at such a high temperature for longer time and the coating was very thin to cover only the active sites of coconut charcoal. Therefore, as soon as the temperature reached 190° , the run was stopped and the column flushed for 3 hr and recharged with Porapak Q column.

Column packed with Porapak Q: The condition of the instrument was as follows:

Column—Porapak Q, $5' \times 1/4''$. Inlet pressure—14 psi hydrogen, Filament current—180 mA, Temp. 70 to 190° for 26 min and thereafter isothermal.

The gas chromatogram of ignition product undistilled (sample III) shows peaks and shoulders numbering 26 out of which first 6 peaks were having no practical resolution except very small shoulders; thereafter they were well resolved with a few exceptions. Out of these, first 6 peaks combined together and other five, i. e., 7 to 10 and 18

are major. They could not be identified due to lack of reference compounds.

The distillate sample IV had all the first 7 peaks clear and thereafter 10 to 13 and also 15 to 17 got combined. In these, the peaks 2, 4, 7, 11 and 16 were the major peaks. The compounds in original and the distillate are more or less the same with variation of concentration which is quite obvious from original. Peak 8 of sample III was not found in distillate sample IV, otherwise retention of the peaks is more or less same. Although it was not possible to identify all the products of the reaction, because of lack of standard reference compounds, it has been possible to ascertain the presence of NO , NO_2 and CO_2 in the gaseous reaction products which will be helpful in elucidating the mechanism of reaction.

Proposed mechanism of the reaction:

The identification of some major products allows the formulation of a probable mechanism. Among the major products, mention may be made of dimethylnitrosamine, dimethylnitramine, dimethylamine, UDMH-nitrate, nitromethane and methyl nitrate. These compounds (most of them) have been detected in both ignition and non-ignition (or near ignition) conditions. Evidences for complete burning are not very sound as the peak near CO_2 in gas chromatography leaves some doubt about its existence in the reaction products. The existence of the several above compounds in the liquid products indicates that at least the C—H and C—N bonds stand the high temperature of burning both in the open air and in a closed bomb calorimeter.

The scheme below is a likely mechanism for the formation of these compounds:

The mechanism proposed above is based on reactions which are known, and on analogous reactions of similar reagents.

The reaction is initiated by the generation of a powerful electrophile NO_2^+ in step (i) and its interaction with UDMH (ii). The abstraction of a hydrogen atom by NO_2 radical is a step proposed by several workers including Sawyer and Glassman². Further reactions (iii) to (v) and decomposition of intermediate products leads to the dimethylamine (E). The amine so formed besides constituting a reaction product in itself, as has been indicated by the results of the various physical methods of analysis, reacts further. The nitrosation of amines by nitrous acid produced in the step (vi) through NO^+ is a well known reaction leading to the formation of nitrosamine.

In the case of hydrazine and methylhydrazine the nitrosamine and nitramine formed would dissociate easily,

and hence nitrosamine was not detected in any of the physical methods of investigation by earlier workers³. But in the case of UDMH the nitrosamine is stabilised.

Besides dimethylamine (E), the UDMH itself may undergo nitrosation by NO^+ or HNO_2 produced in step (iii). The nitrosodimethylhydrazine (H) formed, tautomerises to give the intermediate (I) which decomposes, according to Sidgwick¹¹, to form the amine (E) and N_2O .

However, the intermediate (I) may also decompose to form azides (J) and methanol (K).

Moreover, hydrazine is known to be oxidised by nitrous acid to give hydrazoic acid.

If the same mechanism operates for substituted hydrazines, this reaction should also give methyl azide (J) and methanol from UDMH.

Methanol or CH_3N_3 can react with concentrated HNO_3 to give methyl nitrate.

The preceding derivations are significant in the sense that azides are known to undergo explosive decomposition and the occasional bumpings during

distillation of the liquid product of ignition might be associated with their presence. Nitrosamines are known to react with azides rapidly giving amines, N_2O and N_2 . Therefore, there are little chances of the survival of azides in the reaction mixture.

Now, whenever a H^+ is formed, as in the steps (ii), (vi), (vii) and (viii) it can add to the UDMH molecule giving dimethylhydrazinium ion (M) which, in combination with the nitrate from nitric acid, accounts for the dimethylhydrazinium nitrate (N) observed as a product.

Methanol formed has the other choice of reacting with NO_2 to produce formaldehyde and formic acid. This in turn may lead to a number of side reactions. In the reaction of UDMH with N_2O_4 , Zung *et al*¹² detected, by mass spectrometry, a compound formaldehyde-dimethylhydrazone, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{CH}_2$, supposed to be formed by the interaction of formaldehyde with UDMH itself. No such indication is available in the present investigations.

The mass spectrum of one sample shows a peak at $m/e=112$. It could be assigned to tetramethyl tetrazene formed by dimerisation of the reported diazenium ion $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}^+=\text{N}^-$ ¹³. But there is no evidence of its presence in the ultraviolet spectrum (due possibly to symmetry forbiddenness) where it would be expected to show strong absorption towards longer wave length side due to the conjugated nitrogen chain, $\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{N}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor R. P. Singh, University of Delhi, for the facilities and assistance in recording the various ir and nmr spectra, and to Dr. S. Varma, Manager, Research Wing, P & D Division, F. C. I. Ltd., Sindri for the recording of the mass spectra and gas chromatograms.

References

1. M. A. SAAD, *AIAAJ*, 1972, 10, 1073.
2. R. F. SAWYER and I. GLASSMAN, "Gas-Phase Reactions of Hydrazine with Nitrogen Dioxide, Nitric Oxide and Oxygen", Eleventh International Symposium on Combustion, The Combustion Inst., Pittsburgh, Pa., 1967.
3. S. W. MAYER, D. TAYLOR and L. SCHIELER, "Preignition Products from Storable Propellants at Simulated High Altitude Conditions", TR-9210-02-1, November 1967.
4. T. CHRISTOS *et al*, *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, 1967, 4, 1224.
5. H. E. PERLRE, Private Communication, Aug. 1967, Explosives Research Centre, Bureau of Mines, U. S. Deptt. of Interior, Pittsburgh, Pa.
6. M. A. SAAD and M. B. DETWEILER, *AIAAJ*, 1969, 7, 1588.

SINGH & PRASAD : ANALYSIS OF THE IGNITION PRODUCTS OF UNSYMMETRICAL DIMETHYL ETC.

7. JOHN R. DYER, 'Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds', Prentice-Hall of India, Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1971.
8. C. N. R. RAO *et al.*, "A Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics", East West Press Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, p. 261.
9. K. NAKANISHI. "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy Practical", Holden Day, Inc., San Francisco and Nan Kodo Company Ltd., Tokyo.
10. J. M. TROWELL, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 1971, **9**, 230.
11. SIDGWICK, 'The Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen', Oxford University Press, London, 1942, p. 380.
12. L. B. ZUNG and B. P. BREEN, "A Basic Study of the Ignition of Hypergolic Liquid Propellants", NA7-488, Feb. 1970, Dynamic Science, Irvine, Calif.
13. W. R. MCBRIDE and H. W. KRUSE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 563.